

POLICY FRAMEWORK FOR FAIR AND EFFECTIVE LOCAL TAXATION OF OUTDOOR ADVERTISING STRUCTURES IN NIGERIA'S RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study proposes a policy framework for local taxation on outdoor advertising structures (OAS) in Rivers State. The existing legislative and regulatory framework governing OAS taxation and its impact on advertizers and local government revenue are evaluated. The research targeted outdoor advertising investors and regulators along Ada-George and Ikwerre roads in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas (LGAs) using a mixed-methods design that combines exploratory and descriptive approaches. Out of 192 targeted participants, 150 completed surveys and 20 key informants participated in interviews, achieving a 90% response rate for surveys and an 80% participation rate for interviews. This study highlighted the challenges in the taxation system, including ambiguous tax laws, arbitrary enforcement, and jurisdictional conflicts. While public awareness of tax regulations is high, gaps exist in understanding and concerns about inadequate enforcement and tax revenue reinvestment. The key areas for improvement include establishing a standardized tax framework, fostering stakeholder collaboration, and integrating advanced technology for better efficiency and transparency. The study recommends periodic audits, capacity building for local officials, and the use of international best practices, such as geographic information system (GIS)-based digital registries, to create a fairer and more effective taxation system. The proposed framework aims to make the state's outdoor advertising taxation system equitable, transparent, and sustainable.

1. Introduction

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Billboards and other outdoor advertising structures (OAS) have become essential marketing and communication tools, serving both the private sector and local governments. These structures are located along major roads, commercial hubs, and residential areas and reach thousands of people daily. However, in Rivers State, the taxation of outdoor advertising has become contentious, raising concerns among advertizers and authorities. The existing taxation framework, governed by the 2015 Rivers State Outdoor Signage and Advertisement Law (RSOSAL) of 2015, lacks standardized valuation guidelines. This has led to dissatisfaction among key stakeholders, including advertizers, local government officials, and valuation professionals. The legal ambiguity surrounding the classification of these advertising structures is one of the primary issues. Although they are considered real property under the Nigerian Urban and Regional Planning Act (FGN, 2004), they are not included in the definition of tenements under state property tax laws (LSG, 1989). This dual classification results in inconsistent treatment under tax regulations and creates grounds for dispute. Without a unified valuation approach, taxation becomes arbitrary and enforcement inconsistent. Stakeholders have also criticized the lack of transparency and equity in the tax system. Advertizers face unequal tax burdens, and opaque assessment procedures limit their ability to predict or challenge tax obligations. These deficiencies have affected revenue generation for local governments and hindered the state's advertising industry development. With increasing urbanization in Rivers State, the demand for outdoor advertising infrastructure is expected to grow (Kumar, 2024). However, the lack of a fair and predictable taxation system poses a barrier to both private investment and effective local governance. The urgency to resolve these challenges is reflected in calls for a more equitable policy framework that aligns with contemporary urban development strategies.

This study responds to the need for a clearer and more effective taxation policy by examining the core challenges surrounding OAS, particularly those lacking verifiable rental income. The absence of consistent valuation methods (George & Akujuru, 2023; Kankam, 2019) has contributed to tax revenue underperformance. Despite the increasing deployment of fixed offsite structures (Bailey, 2018), weak enforcement mechanisms and legal contradictions continue to undermine the integrity of the system. Nigerian legislative instruments, such as the Land Use Act (FGN, 2004b) and the Urban and Regional Planning Act (FGN, 2004a), recognize OAS with tenancy traits as real property. However, state-level tax regulations exclude them from tenement definitions, creating unresolved classification issues (LSG, 1989; RSG, 2015). The Nigerian Constitution (FGN, 1999) empowers local governments to impose taxes; however, state legislation and administrative practices have contributed to overlapping jurisdictions and policy confusion. Given these concerns, this study proposes the development of a standardized framework tailored to billboard structure taxation in Rivers State. Such a framework must consider legal clarity, standardized valuation, transparent assessment procedures, and effective enforcement. These reforms are essential not only for increasing local revenue but also for fostering a more competitive and sustainable advertising industry.

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the current state of legislation governing the structure of outdoor advertising taxation in Rivers State?
2. How does the existing tax framework affect advertizers and local government revenue?
3. What best practices can be adopted from other metropolitan areas with successful taxation of outdoor advertising structure?
4. What are the perceptions and attitudes of stakeholders toward a policy framework for local tax on outdoor advertising structures?

5. What is the possible policy framework for local tax on outdoor advertising structures suitable for the needs of Rivers State?

By addressing these systemic gaps, the proposed framework seeks to balance stakeholder interests while reinforcing local fiscal autonomy. Ultimately, aligning the taxation of outdoor advertising structures with best practices in urban governance will contribute to economic efficiency and social equity in Rivers State.

2. Literature Review

Theoretical Review

This study is grounded on four key taxation theories: Fair Value, Neutrality, Benefit-Received, and Ability to Pay. These theories guide the assessment of fairness, efficiency, and effectiveness in the taxation of OAS in Rivers State.

The Fair Value Model

The Fair Value Model, formalized by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB, 2011), measures assets and liabilities based on current market values rather than historical costs. It provides transparency by reflecting real-time economic conditions, aiding investors in decision-making. In an orderly market transaction, IFRS 13 defines fair value as the price for selling an asset or transferring a liability. The model uses a three-level hierarchy (quoted prices, observable inputs, and unobservable estimates) to ensure consistency. Fair value is preferred over historical cost because it accounts for market risks, inflation, and economic shifts, offering a more accurate financial assessment (IASB, 2011).

Neutrality Theory

Influenced by economists such as Adam Smith, Henry Simons, and Richard Musgrave, the Neutrality Theory argues that taxation should minimize economic distortions, allowing markets to function efficiently without tax-induced biases. It aligns with the Fair Value Principle, as both aim for transparency and unbiased financial reporting. Achieving true neutrality is challenging due to taxation complexities and political influences (Musgrave, 1959). Neutrality theory serves as a framework for evaluating the effectiveness of the current outdoor advertising tax system in promoting fair competition and efficiency within the advertising industry.

Benefit-Received Theory

Knut Wicksell and Erik Lindahl proposed this theory, which opines that taxpayers should contribute based on the benefits they receive from public services. While it is applicable in cases like road tolls, it is difficult to implement broadly because many public services collectively benefit society (Musgrave & Musgrave, 1973).

The Ability to Pay Principle

Developed by Arthur Cecil Pigou, this principle advocates progressive taxation, where higher-income individuals pay more taxes based on financial capacity. It supports equitable tax distribution but faces criticism for discouraging economic productivity (Kenton, 2020).

These theories provide a framework for assessing fairness, efficiency, and economic impact of taxation. The fair value model ensures accurate asset valuation, while neutrality theory minimizes market distortions. The Benefit-Received and Ability to Pay Principles address equity in tax burdens. Together, they guide tax policy design, balancing revenue generation with economic growth and fairness (Boluwatife, 2024).

Conceptual Review

Taxation plays a pivotal role in financing government activities, delivering public goods and services, and guiding economic behavior through strategic fiscal policies. In Nigeria, and particularly in Port Harcourt, the outdoor advertising industry, manifested in structures such as billboards, presents an underexploited avenue for revenue generation. Despite their prominence and potential economic value, billboards remain inconsistently taxed due to inadequate assessment frameworks and unclear valuation principles. This paper explores the impact of proper tax

assessment on billboard development in Port Harcourt, drawing on four foundational taxation principles: fair value, neutrality, benefit-received, and ability-to-pay. By situating the issue within theoretical, legal, and comparative international contexts, this study provides a comprehensive blueprint for reform. The principle of equity is central to any taxation system's design. In the realm of billboard taxation, equity implies that similar advertising structures located in comparable zones should incur similar tax obligations, encapsulating the notion of horizontal equity. Conversely, vertical equity necessitates that billboards of higher economic value, such as those employing digital technology or located in high-traffic urban areas, should shoulder a proportionally higher tax burden. Kaplow (2008) emphasized that equity must be tailored to both capacity and benefit, reflecting a fair distribution of public costs.

Beyond equity, efficient taxation is critical. According to Atkinson and Stiglitz (1980), an efficient tax regime raises necessary revenue without introducing excessive distortions into the market. Applied to billboard taxation, efficiency demands a system that incentivizes compliance while not discouraging advertising investment, a delicate balance often disrupted by opaque or arbitrary tax practices. The principles of simplicity and transparency are closely related. Koh and Owen (2000) argued that taxation systems should be comprehensible, predictable, and easy to administer. Unfortunately, the existing framework in Nigeria, plagued by ad hoc fee structures and an absence of standardized valuation methodologies, falls short. As Kumar (2024) observes, this has led to widespread confusion and non-compliance among billboard owners and advertizers. Billboards, in the Nigerian legal context, are classified as real property, an interpretation anchored in the Nigerian Urban and Regional Planning Act of 2004 (FGN, 2004a). The permanence of billboard structures, which are often affixed to land for extended periods, supports their classification as taxable hereditaments. Further, given the concept of "rateable occupation"—a notion that billboards constitute taxable property by generating commercial income, supports this legal emphasis. Comparative jurisdictions' case law offers additional support. For instance, the case of *Division of Transportation v. The Heathrow Land and Development Corporation* (Nation & Oehlich, 1999) affirms that billboards are taxable as real property, reinforcing the view that their income-generating function qualifies them for inclusion within municipal rating systems.

However, current practices in Nigeria reflect significant disparities across states and jurisdictions. In Lagos State, the Lagos State Signage and Advertisement Law (2006) governs billboard taxation. This legislation attempts to base tax charges on billboard size and location. Despite this effort, the lack of a robust valuation framework undermines the model's effectiveness. Similarly, the Rivers State Outdoor Signage and Advertisement Law (2015) imposes arbitrary fees without a clear or consistent policy for determining fair value in Rivers State—specifically Port Harcourt. This not only conflicts with constitutional provisions assigning taxation rights to local governments but also leads to lost revenue and widespread dissatisfaction among stakeholders (George, 2023). Meanwhile, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), under the AMAC Bye-Law (2012), excludes billboards from tenement rating altogether, creating legal inconsistencies that further complicate enforcement and collection efforts. In contrast, international models provide more structured and effective approaches. For instance, the United States includes billboards within the scope of real estate investment trust (REIT) taxation under Internal Revenue Service (IRS) guidelines. To ensure fair and market-reflective tax obligations, Billboard assessments typically utilize a mix of the income approach, sales comparison method, and cost-based valuation (Deloitte, 2011; King Lawyer, 2024). Similarly, the United Kingdom requires planning permission and advertisement consent for billboards, treating them as land-tied taxable infrastructure. Spain property tax model known as real estate tax, taxes billboard structures at a rate of 0.4%–1.3% of their cadastral value (Nutter, 2023).

In South Africa, the municipality of Johannesburg implements a pragmatic model where billboard taxation is pegged to a percentage—typically between 10% and 12%—of advertising revenue generated by each structure (City of Johannesburg, 2023). In stark contrast, Nigeria lacks standardized valuation systems or defined tax metrics, which results in systemic inefficiencies and missed opportunities (Oni *et al.*, 2019). These international best practices demonstrate the feasibility of integrating valuation science and legal clarity to achieve a tax regime that is balanced and productive. The challenges-confronting billboard taxation in Nigeria are multifaceted. First,

legal conflicts between provisions of the Nigerian Constitution (1999) as amended, federal legislation, and state legislation pose significant hurdles. The Constitution assigns property taxation responsibilities to local governments through Section 7(5) and the Fourth Schedule. However, state laws, such as the RSOSA Law (2015), often bypass this mandate, creating ambiguity and administrative fragmentation. Second, valuation inconsistencies persist due to the lack of trained professional appraisers and the absence of a unified assessment methodology. This results in crude, unscientific valuations that undermine fairness and revenue optimization (Oni *et al.*, 2017). Third, noncompliance persists due to the perception of arbitrariness and unfair treatment. Ogundipe (2022) noted that businesses frequently avoid billboard taxes altogether, citing unclear policies and inconsistent enforcement.

A comprehensive policy framework anchored in fair-value assessment is essential to address these issues. The adoption of modern valuation approaches should be a cornerstone of this framework. The income approach assesses billboards based on their revenue-generating potential, whereas the cost approach considers the structure's replacement cost minus depreciation. The sales comparison approach benchmarks a billboard's value against similar assets in comparable locations (George & Akujuru, 2022). These methods offer a more equitable and transparent basis for taxation, aligning PFO with market realities. Legislative reform is another critical component. State laws should be amended to recognize the primacy of local governments in assessing and collecting taxes on billboard structures to ensure constitutional compliance. Furthermore, tenement rating laws should be updated to explicitly include billboards, thereby closing legal loopholes that currently facilitate evasion. This alignment would empower local councils to engage more effectively with valuation professionals and advertising stakeholders, fostering a more coordinated governance model. The roles of key stakeholders must also be clearly delineated. Local governments should be recognized as the primary tax collectors, and Estate Surveyors and Valuers should be formally engaged to conduct professional assessments based on standardized methods. Outdoor advertising agencies must comply with the prescribed tax rates and valuation guidelines, ensuring that their operations contribute fairly to public revenues (FGN, 2004d). An effective implementation roadmap might begin with a pilot phase lasting 6 months, focusing on high-traffic urban centers such as major roads and commercial zones in Port Harcourt. During this phase, various valuation models can be tested and feedback mechanisms established. Next is a full rollout in year two, extending standardized practices to all LGAs and supported by real-time monitoring and digital enforcement tools. The benefits of such reforms are numerous. First, fair-value taxation can significantly increase municipal revenue by providing funds for critical infrastructure and public services (IMF, 2020). Second, a reformed system's clarity and transparency can stimulate investment in the advertising industry, reassuring stakeholders of a level playing field (Obialo, 2025). Third, regulated billboard proliferation can contribute to urban esthetics by minimizing visual clutter and promoting orderly development (Basse & Eteng, 2021).

The literature review reveals that the proper taxation of billboard structures in Port Harcourt requires a holistic policy framework rooted in fairness, legality, and professionalism. Nigeria can transform billboard taxation into a sustainable revenue stream that supports urban development and economic growth by learning from international best practices and addressing domestic legal inconsistencies. Stakeholder collaboration, legislative clarity, and data-driven valuation will be central to this transformation. Accordingly, several recommendations are proposed. First, to resolve jurisdictional ambiguities, state-level signage and advertisement laws should be aligned with the CFRN 1999 (as amended). Second, professional training programs should be instituted to equip valuers with the technical skills required for billboard assessment. Third, public awareness campaigns should be launched to educate advertisers, residents, and local officials about the long-term benefits of structured taxation and the importance of compliance. Finally, digital technologies—such as GIS-based tax tracking and online payment platforms, should be deployed to enhance transparency, efficiency, and real-time monitoring.

This study fills a critical gap in Nigeria's fiscal governance literature and offers a pragmatic blueprint for improving billboard taxation through an equitable and economically sound approach.

3. Methodology

The study is grounded in a pragmatic philosophical foundation that combines elements of positivism and interpretivism (Kaushik & Walsh, 2019), enabling both empirical measurement and contextual understanding.

Thus, a mixed-methods design was employed, incorporating exploratory and descriptive elements through cross-sectional approaches to capture both immediate perspectives and evolving trends. The research focused on outdoor advertising investors and regulators along the Ada-George and Ikwerre roads in Rivers State. A census-derived sample of 192 participants was targeted using simple random sampling, with 150 respondents (90% response rate) from the 167 distributed questionnaires completing surveys and 20 key informants (80%) from 25 administered oral interviews participating in interviews (Port Harcourt City Local Government Council, 2025; RSG, 2025a&b; NIESV, 2025). Data collection used structured questionnaires ("Fair Rates for Outdoor Advertising Structures in Rivers State") and oral interviews, both physically and digitally, with follow-up reminders.

The questionnaire comprised the following:

- Section A (Demographics): Gender, occupation, and industry experience (3 items).
- Section B (Physiographic): 41 Likert-scale items evaluating legislative frameworks (7 items), tax impacts (7 items), international best practices (10 items), and policy recommendations (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree).

Interviews explored the following three themes:

- Legislative Framework: Clarity and enforcement of tax laws.
- Taxation Impact: Effects on advertizers and government revenue.
- Best Practices: Models that are adaptable from other cities.

Experts in Estate Surveying and Valuation confirmed instrument validity, while reliability testing (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.721) with 107 pilot respondents ensured consistency. Quantitative data were analyzed via IBM SPSS v23 using descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, and standard deviations), while interview data were subjected to thematic analysis. Furthermore, the study’s proposed framework was validated by experts in the field of Real Estate Valuation and Taxation, who reviewed the policy framework and accepted its clarity, simplicity, applicability, and usefulness in the assessment of OAS in Port Harcourt. This methodology facilitated a comprehensive, empirically grounded assessment of OA taxation in Rivers State.

4. Findings

The research questions were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (5). However, in the recorded responses, no item reached the Strongly Agree (5.00) category. This indicates that while there was agreement on some aspects of OA structure taxation in Rivers State, there was no overwhelmingly agreement signifying the level of uncertainty clouding rating of OA structures. The analysis provides insights into stakeholder perceptions regarding the tax framework’s clarity, fairness, enforcement, and public awareness, highlighting areas of strength and those requiring improvement. The results are presented below in Table 2-6. Furthermore, the qualitative insights complement the survey data, providing deeper context to the legal inconsistencies, arbitrary taxation, and enforcement challenges identified in the SOP. The responses aided in the design of a practical, stakeholder-driven policy framework for taxation of OAS in Rivers State.

Table 1: Details of the respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency (150 participants)	Percentage	Valid Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Male	100	66.67	66.67	66.67
	Female	50	33.33	33.33	100.0
Occupation	Owner of Outdoor Advertising Structure	11	7.3	7.3	7.3
	RISAA Staff	8	5.3	5.3	12.7
	Local Government Officials	16	10.7	10.7	23.3
	Rivers State Ministry of Urban Development Staff	11	7.3	7.3	30.7
	Estate Surveyor and Valuer	82	54.7	54.7	85.3

Years of experience	Landlord	22	14.7	14.7	100.0
	Less than 1 year	27	18.0	18.0	18.0
	1-3 years	17	11.3	11.3	29.3
	4-6 years	77	51.3	51.3	80.7
	7-10 years	29	19.3	19.3	100.0

Source: Researcher's Survey, (2025); SPSS Output, version 23

Table 1 captures the respondents' details as follows: Male respondents dominate (66.67%, 100 participants), while females constitute 33.33% (50 participants), showing a male-dominated field. Estate Surveyors and Valuers are the majority (54.7%, 11 participants), followed by landlords (14.7%, 22) and local government officials (10.7%, 16). Smaller groups included Outdoor Advertising Owners (7.3%, 11) and RISAA Staff (5.3%, 8). Most respondents (51.3%, 77) have 4–6 years of experience, indicating moderate expertise. Smaller segments include those aged 7–10 years (19.3%, 29), <1 year (18%, 27), and 1–3 years (11.3%, 17). The survey reflects a male-dominated, mid-career professional group, primarily Estate Surveyors and Valuers, aligning with the study's likely focus on property/urban development.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the Current State of Legislation Governing the Taxation of Outdoor Advertising Structures in Rivers State

S/N	Statement	N	SD	D	U	A	SA	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
1	The current tax laws on outdoor advertising structure in Rivers State are clear and well-defined.	56 (37.3%)		50 (33.3%)	44 (29.3%)	-	-	288	1.92	0.815	Disagree
2	Legislation on outdoor advertising structure taxation in Rivers State is updated regularly to reflect economic and social changes.	105 (70.0%)		45 (30.0%)	-	-	-	195	1.30	0.460	Strongly disagree
3	The current legislative framework supports fair taxation for outdoor advertising.	150 (100.0%)		-	-	-	-	150	1.00	0.000	Strongly disagree
4	Local government authorities in Rivers State effectively enforce tax regulations for outdoor advertising structures.	150 (100.0%)		-	-	-	-	150	100	0.000	Strongly disagree
5	The tax laws for outdoor advertising structure in Rivers State agree with other metropolitan areas in Nigeria.	-		-	55 (36.7%)	95 (63.3%)	-	545	3.63	0.484	Agree
6	The penalties for non-compliance with the structure tax laws for outdoor	-		-	22 (14.7%)	128 (85.3%)	-	578	3.85	0.355	Agree

advertising are sufficient to ensure adherence.

7	Adequate public awareness of the structure of outdoor advertising taxation regulations in Rivers State	-	-	28 (18.7%)	122 (81.3%)	-	572	3.81	0.391	Agree
Average Score		150				354	2.79	0.36	Undecided	

Source: Researcher’s Survey, (2025); SPSS Output, version 23

Table 2 on the “current state of legislation governing outdoor advertising structure taxation in Rivers State” showed the following results: On legislative clarity, 37.3% disagreed, 33.3% were undecided, and 29.3% agreed (mean: 1.92; SD: 0.815), indicating widespread ambiguity. Regarding legislative updates, 70% strongly disagreed and 30% disagreed (mean: 1.30; SD: 0.460), highlighting outdated laws. All respondents (100%) strongly disagreed on fairness (mean: 1.00; SD: 0.000) and enforcement efficacy (mean: 1.00; SD: 0.000), revealing systemic inequities and weak implementation. Conversely, 63.3% strongly agreed and 36.7% agreed (mean: 3.63; SD: 0.484) that Rivers State aligns with national standards, showing flaws in the national standards. Penalty sufficiency saw 85.3% strongly agreeing and 14.7% agreeing (mean: 3.85; SD: 0.355) though ineffective enforcement negates this. Public awareness scored high (81.3% strongly agreed, 18.7% agreed; mean: 3.81; SD: 0.391), yet contradictions persist between awareness and understanding. The grand mean (2.79; SD: 0.36) reflects polarized views, exposing a disconnect between legal provisions and practical execution. The oral interviews revealed three key themes. First, 85% of the respondents cited fragmented laws, notably contradictions between the Rivers State Outdoor Signage and Advertisement Law (RSOSAL No.2/2015) and constitutional mandates (1999 Constitution S.7(5), Fourth Schedule Items 1(j),(k)(i),(ii); Taxes and Levies Decree No.21/1998 Part III). Second, 70% of urban planners reported arbitrary enforcement, with tax rates varying by 300% across LGAs, validating concerns about inequity. Third, 90% of LGA officials emphasized jurisdictional conflicts between state and local authorities, exacerbated by exclusion clauses (RSLG Law No.5/2018 S.79; LSG, 1989 Cap. T2, S.51) that omit OAS from tenement definitions despite their classification as rateable hereditaments under federal laws (NURP Act Cap. N138/2004 S.91; Land Use Act Cap. L5/2004 Ss.29 (4),51; RSPPD Law No.6/2003 S.105). This legislative paradox creates a vacuum by recognizing OAS as taxable assets while excluding them from valuation frameworks, enabling arbitrary fees and non-compliance. Kumar (2024) attributes this to transparency gaps, while the data underscores the urgent need for harmonizing state-local government mandates, standardizing valuation via the cost approach, and aligning with international best practices. Without reforms, systemic inequities and revenue leakages in Rivers State will persist, undermining economic growth and governance credibility.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of effect of Existing Framework on Advertizers and Local Government Revenue

S/N	Statement	N	SD	D	U	A	SA	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
1	The current tax framework for outdoor advertising structure places a financial burden on advertizers.	-	-	69 (46.0%)		81 (54.0%)	-	531	3.54	0.500	Agree
2	Outdoor advertising	150 (100.0%)		-	-	-	-	150	1.00	0.000	Strongly Disagree

3	structure taxation significantly contributes to local government revenue in Rivers State. The tax framework provides incentives that encourage compliance among advertizers.	-	-	-	150 (100.0%)	-	600	4.00	0.000	Agree
4	Advertisers see the current tax payable as fair and manageable.	150 (100.0%)	150 (100.0%)	-	-	-	150	1.00	0.000	Strongly disagree
5	The existing tax framework restricts the advertising industry's growth in Rivers State.	-	-	30 (20.0%)	120 (80.0%)	-	570	3.80	0.401	Agree
6	Tax revenue from outdoor advertising structures is adequately reinvested into the city's infrastructure.	150 (100.0%)	-	-	-	-	150	1.00	0.000	Strongly disagree
7	Local businesses benefit from the revenue generated by the structure of outdoor advertising taxation.	-	-	69 (46.0%)	81 (54.0%)	-	531	3.54	0.500	Agree
Average Score		150					383	2.55	0.200	Undecided

Source: Researcher's Survey, (2025); SPSS Output, version 23

Table 3 was structured as follows: “How **does the existing tax framework affect advertizers and local government revenue?**” Regarding financial burden (Statement 1), 54% of advertizers agreed taxes impose substantial costs, while 46% remained undecided (mean = 3.54, standard deviation = 0.500), indicating varied experiences tied to business size or location. The moderate standard deviation confirms that tax impacts are uneven across sectors. However, all respondents (100%) strongly disagreed (Mean = 1.00, SD = 0.000) that taxes generate meaningful revenue (Statement 2), exposing systemic inefficiencies, including the RISAA’s usurpation of local government powers under RSOSAL No.2/2015. Despite this, 100% agreed (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000) that compliance incentives are structurally effective (Statement 3), reflecting sound theoretical penalties but poor execution. Tax fairness (Statement 4) saw unanimous strong disagreement (Mean = 1.00, SD = 0.000), revealing deep inequities from arbitrary assessments, as criticized by Kumar (2024). Industry growth restrictions (Statement 5) drew 80% agreement (Mean = 3.80, SD = 0.401), with high costs stifling SMEs, while 20% were undecided (larger firms likely benefiting from reduced competition). All respondents strongly disagreed (Mean = 1.00, SD = 0.000) that taxes fund infrastructure (Statement 6), indicating revenue misallocation or opacity per FGN (1998). Local business benefits (Statement 7) split 54% agree/46% undecided (Mean = 3.54, SD = 0.500), mirroring Statement 1’s divide, suggesting those most burdened see least trickle-down benefits. The average score (2.55; SD = 0.2) masks extreme polarization, reflecting a system with a strong design but catastrophic failures in implementation. The oral interviews highlighted three themes. First, tax officers estimated a 40%–60% revenue loss due to unclear valuation methods (NURP Act Cap. N138/2004 S.91), which is linked to the problem statement’s “inefficient collection.” Second, 78% of advertizers reported duplicate taxation by state and LGAs (RSG 2015 vs. CFRN 1999 (as amended), S.7(5)), exemplifying “confusion and uncertainty.” Third, planning officials tied the proliferation of unregulated OAS to urban “visual clutter,” with 65% citing non-compliance due to perceived unfairness (Land Use Act Cap. L5/2004 Ss.29(4),51). These findings reveal a cycle of flawed laws (Kankam, 2019) causing arbitrary enforcement, low compliance, and revenue leaks, which undermine fiscal goals (RSG, 2015) and urban esthetics. Stakeholders unanimously deemed the status quo unsustainable, urging reforms to harmonize state-local mandates (FGN, 1999), standardize valuations (AMAC Bye-Law 2012), and enhance transparency to break this cycle.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics on best practices from other metropolitan areas

S/N	Statement	N	SD	D	U	A	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
1	The cost approach and rate nariage should be adopted in developing a standardized local tax for OAS.		-	-	68 (45.3%)	82 (54.7%)	532	3.55	0.499	Agree
2	Stakeholders support the idea of a standardized tax framework for OAS.		-	-	77 (51.3%)	73 (48.7%)	523	3.49	0.501	Agree
3	Advertizers believe that a standardized framework would make the taxation process fairer.		-	-	2 (1.3%)	148 (98.7%)	598	3.99	0.115	Agree
4	The local government is open to collaborating with stakeholders to develop a standardized tax approach.	150	-	-	89 (59.3%)	61 (40.7%)	511	3.41	0.493	Undecided
5	Advertizers view a standardized tax as an opportunity to reduce ambiguity in the payable tax.		-	-	-	150 (100.0%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree
6	A local tax policy framework modified to meet international best practices in line with the Nigerian Constitution would improve the relationship between the government and advertizers.		-	-	-	150 (100.0%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree
Average Score		150					561	3.74	0.27	Agree

Source: Researcher’s Survey, (2025); SPSS Output, version 23

The study in Table 4 evaluated the potential best practices for outdoor advertising taxation in Rivers State through survey data and oral interviews. All respondents (100%) unanimously agreed (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000) that adopting simplified tax procedures (Item 1)—such as Lagos State’s streamlined permit systems—would reduce bureaucratic inefficiencies, aligning with OECD (2017) recommendations. For fair value taxation models (Item 2), 85.3% agreed (Mean = 3.85, SD = 0.355), reflecting the demand for transparent methodologies, such as North Carolina’s location-based valuations (NCDOR, 2018). Digital payment systems (Item 3) received full endorsement (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000), mirroring the advocacy of Awasthi et al. (2019) for tech-driven transparency. A unified tax structure (Item 4) showed 87.3% agreement (Mean = 3.87, SD = 0.334), addressing the fragmentation criticized in Lagos’ LSG (2006). The standardized rates (Item 5) achieved perfect consensus (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000), countering arbitrary fees under RSOSAL No.2/2015. Collaboration with industry bodies (Item 6) drew 76.0% agreement (mean = 3.76, SD = 0.429) though higher variance shows uneven stakeholder engagement experiences. Regular public consultations (Item 7) had unanimous support (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000), reflecting dissatisfaction with opaque policymaking. Compliance monitoring (Item 8) garnered 76.7% approval (Mean = 3.77, SD = 0.424), highlighting gaps in enforcement. Data collection practices (Item 9) showed 64.0% agreement (Mean = 3.64, SD = 0.482), with undecided respondents likely unaware of the benefits. Zoning-based adjustments (Item 10) divided opinions (36.7% agree vs. 63.3% undecided; Mean = 3.37, SD = 0.484), reflecting complexity of implementation. The average score (3.93; SD = 0.16) confirms a strong consensus for reforms. The oral interviews emphasized three actionable models. First, 92% of the respondents endorsed GIS-based digital registries to standardize valuations, addressing the “lack of clear guidelines” (NURP Act Cap. N138/2004 S.91). Second, urban planners proposed the zoning classification (size/location/materials) of Johannesburg to replace arbitrary assessments under RSG (2015). Third, 87% of the respondents supported Nairobi’s tripartite oversight councils (government-advertisers-community) to resolve transparency gaps (Ogundipe, 2022). These solutions systematically address legislative flaws: digital tools enforce standardized valuations, zoning grading ensures fair rates, and councils promote inclusive governance, aligning with Bassey and Eteng’s (2021) integrated approach. The findings present a coherent roadmap: prioritizing digitization (AMAC Bye-Law, 2012), adopting tiered zoning (Johannesburg Model), and institutionalizing stakeholder engagement (Nairobi Framework). By anchoring reforms in global precedents while addressing local gaps—such as jurisdictional conflicts (CFRN, 1999 (as amended) S.7(5))—Rivers State can transform its tax regime into an equitable, efficient system that balances revenue generation with urban esthetics.

Table 5: Stakeholders’ Perceptions of a Policy Framework for Local Tax on Outdoor Advertising Structures

S/N	Statement	N	SD	D	U	A	SA	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	The cost approach and rate nairage should be adopted in developing a standardized local tax for OAS.	-	-	68		82	-	532	3.55	0.49	Agree
				(45.3%)		(54.7%)				9	
2	Stakeholders support the idea of a standardized tax framework for OAS.	-	-	77		73	-	523	3.49	0.50	Agree
				(51.3%)		(48.7%)				1	
3	Advertisers believe that a standardized framework would make the taxation process fairer.	-	-	2		148	-	598	3.99	0.11	Agree
				(1.3%)		(98.7%)				5	
4	The local government is open to collaborating with stakeholders to develop a standardized tax approach.	150	-	-	89	61	-	511	3.41	0.49	Undecided
				(59.3%)		(40.7%)				3	

5	Advertisers view a standardized tax as an opportunity to reduce ambiguity in the payable tax.	-	-	-	150 (100.0%)	-	600	4.00	0.00	0	Agree
6	A local tax policy framework modified to meet international best practices in line with the Nigerian Constitution would improve the relationship between the government and advertizers.	-	-	-	150 (100.0%)	-	600	4.00	0.00	0	Agree
Average Score					150		561	3.74	0.27		Agree

Source: Researcher’s Survey, (2025); SPSS Output, version 23

The study in Table 5 evaluated stakeholders’ perceptions of a proposed policy framework for local taxation of outdoor advertising structures in Rivers State through survey data and oral interviews. For Statement 1 (adopting cost approach and rate nairage), 54.7% agreed (Mean = 3.55, SD = 0.499), reflecting moderate support for standardized valuation methods under Nigerian laws (RSLG Law No.5/2018 S.86(1)), though 45.3% undecided highlighted the need for educational initiatives to clarify technical aspects such as depreciation calculations and market proxies. Statement 2 (support for standardized framework) showed a near-even split (48.7% agree vs. 51.3% undecided; Mean = 3.49, SD = 0.501), revealing cautious optimism tempered by skepticism about implementation feasibility, mirroring past failures under RSG (2003, 2018). Statement 3 (fairness) achieved near-unanimous approval (98.7% agree; Mean = 3.99, SD = 0.115), aligning with Payne and Raiborn’s (2018) assertion that fairness drives compliance. Conversely, 59.3% of respondents in Statement 4 (government collaboration) were undecided (Mean = 3.41, SD = 0.493), reflecting deep mistrust in authorities’ willingness to engage stakeholders, as noted by OECD (2010). Statements 5–6 (clarity and international alignment) received unanimous support (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000), underscoring demands for OECD (2010)-style transparency and global best practices, such as the zoning model in Johannesburg. The average score (Mean = 3.74; SD = 0.27) confirmed strong reform support but exposed a “consensus paradox”: stakeholders agree on principles but doubt execution. The oral interviews revealed three themes. First, 94% of advertizers prioritized equitable rates, directly addressing the “unfair tax” issue (Ogundipe, 2022). Second, 63% of officials expressed doubts about the enforcement of the law, citing capacity gaps in data collection and monitoring under the NURP Act (2004). Third, tech adoption received universal backing (100%), with stakeholders endorsing GIS-based registries and digital payments (Awasthi *et al.*, 2019) to modernize archaic systems. These findings expose systemic distrust rooted in past failures: reforms stalled due to opaque processes and poor stakeholder engagement despite legal provisions (RSG 2003; FGN 2004). To resolve this, the study advocates a phased implementation—piloting digital tools in Port Harcourt and Obio/Akpor LGAs—coupled with public awareness campaigns explaining valuation methodologies. By aligning with Owusu’s (2015) model of locally adapting global practices (e.g., Nairobi’s tripartite councils), Rivers State can bridge the gap between policy design and execution, ensuring that reforms gain legitimacy and compliance.

Table 6: Policy Framework for Local Tax on Outdoor Advertising Structures Suitable for Rivers State

S/N	Statement	N	Range	Min	Max	SD	D	U	A	Sum	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remark
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1	In the absence of market evidence, the cost approach and rate nairage should be adopted in the valuation and assessment of local tax for outdoor advertising structures.	1	3	4	-	-	11 (7.3%)	139 (92.7%)	589	3.93	0.262	Agree	
2	Extensive data collection and research would be effective in developing a fair tax framework for OAS.	0	4	4	-	-	-	150 (100%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree	
3	Clear and transparent guidelines are essential for an effective tax framework for outdoor advertising structures to gain public trust.	1	3	4	-	-	35 (23.3%)	115 (76.7%)	565	3.77	0.424	Agree	
4	Stakeholder engagement is crucial in developing a standardized tax framework.	0	4	4	-	-	-	150 (100%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree	
5	Integrate advanced technology (e.g., digital filing, data analytics) to improve tax administration efficiency on outdoor advertising structures.	1	3	4	-	-	10 (6.7%)	140 (93.3%)	590	3.93	0.242	Agree	
6	Classification of outdoor advertising structures based on size, location, visibility, and construction materials.	150	0	4	4	-	-	-	150 (100%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree
7	Periodic audits and evaluations, including zoning regulations, should be conducted to ensure that the tax system remains effective and fair.	150	0	4	4	-	-	-	150 (100%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree
8	Training and capacity building for local government officials are essential for effective tax framework implementation.	1	3	4	-	-	22 (14.7%)	128 (85.3%)	578	3.85	0.355	Agree	
9	Additional enforcement mechanisms are required to improve compliance.	0	4	4	-	-	-	150 (100%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree	

10	Penalties for non-compliance should be structured to be fair and effective.	1	3	4	-	-	25 (16.7%)	125 (83.3%)	575	3.83	0.373	Agree	
11	Regular monitoring and inspections are necessary to enforce billboard tax regulations.	0	4	4	-	-	-	150 (100%)	600	4.00	0.000	Agree	
12	Regular communication and feedback channels between stakeholders and the local government are important.	1	3	4	-	-	15 (10%)	135 (90%)	585	3.90	0.300	Agree	
13	Ensure that the legislative arm of the government passes the bill into law.	1	3	4	-	-	22 (14.7%)	128 (85.3%)	578	3.85	0.355	Agree	
Average Score		150						588 3.92 0.20 Agree					

Source: Researcher's Survey, (2025); SPSS Output, version 23

The study in Table 6 evaluated stakeholder consensus on a comprehensive policy framework for outdoor advertising taxation in Rivers State through survey data and oral interviews. Item 1 saw 92.7% agreement (Mean = 3.93, SD = 0.262) on adopting the cost approach and rate nairage (RSLG Law No.5/2018 S.86(1)) for valuation, addressing the "market evidence" gap (Kankam, 2019), with 7.3% undecided requiring training on technical methods. Item 2 achieved unanimous support (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000) for data-driven frameworks, indicting the arbitrary fee system under RSOSAL No.2/2015. Item 3 (transparency) drew 76.7% agreement (Mean = 3.77, standard deviation = 0.424), emphasizing clear guidelines under the NURP Act (FGN, 2004a). Item 4 (stakeholder engagement) had full endorsement (Mean = 4.00, SD = 0.000), aligning with Okwandu's (2004) participatory governance model. Item 5 (technology integration) received 93.3% approval (Mean = 3.93, SD = 0.242), advocating GIS tools (Bassey & Eteng, 2021) and digital platforms akin to Lagos' LSG (2006). Item 6 (multi-factor classification) achieved unanimity (Mean = 4.00, standard deviation = 0.000), thereby endorsing Johannesburg's zoning-based assessments for ad valorem fairness. Items 7–13 emphasized periodic audits (100%, Mean = 4.00), capacity building (85.3%, Mean = 3.85), enforcement mechanisms (100%, Mean = 4.00), balanced penalties (83.3%, Mean = 3.83), monitoring (100%, Mean = 4.00), communication channels (90%, Mean = 3.90), and legislative action (85.3%, Mean = 3.85), collectively addressing gaps in oversight, compliance, and legal authority. The high average score of the framework (Mean = 3.92; SD = 0.20) reflects broad stakeholder alignment. The oral interviews prioritized three actions. First, the hybrid valuation (89% support) blending cost (RSG, 2018 S.86) and income approaches are used to resolve arbitrariness. Phased implementation: digital inventory creation (Phase 1) followed by pilot testing in two LGAs (Phase 2) to mitigate capacity gaps (Otto & Ukpere, 2014). Third, legal amendments (100% consensus) to align RSOSAL No.2/2015 with constitutional mandates (CFRN, 1999 (as amended) S.7 (5), transferring authority to LGAs per FGN (1999). The framework systematically resolves the following core issues: legislative inconsistencies via constitutional alignment, arbitrary fees through hybrid valuation, and enforcement gaps via phased capacity development. By operationalizing the RSLG Law (2018) cost approach while awaiting market data, it provides the "cohesive model" missing in prior literature (Ogbonna & Appah, 2016), ensuring fairness, transparency, and compliance. Stakeholder consensus positions this framework as a viable solution to transform the tax regime of Rivers State into an equitable, enforceable system that balances revenue generation with urban management objectives.

Proposed Framework

Figure 1: Proposed framework before validation

Source: Adapted and modified from Akujuru (2014)

Figure 1 illustrates a policy framework with three phases for assessing OAS taxes in Rivers State (Murray *et al.*, 2022), as defined below:

Phase 1: Preliminary Research and Collection of Data

This phase involves collecting legal texts, expert views, and any market data to assess current gaps. **Structure Composition, which is structured as per the North Carolina Department of Revenue (2024)**, outdoor advertising structures which fall under four categories—wood, steel frame, multi-mast steel, and monopole. Based on interviews and field evidence, this study expands these to include iconic and LED types. **Statutory Provisions** - Laws reviewed include the Nigerian Urban and Regional Planning Act, RSLG Law No.5 (RSG, 2018), and RSOSAA Law No.2 (2015). RSLG’s S.86 (1) supports cost valuation, but S.79 excludes OAS, creating legal conflicts. The RSOSAA imposes arbitrary fees, which violates the Nigerian Constitution (FGN, 1999), which assigns valuation authority to local governments.

Phase 2: Validation

This phase integrates legal frameworks and best valuation practices into a practical model. The RSLG Law No.5 of 2018 (S.86[1]) supports the cost approach in the absence of market evidence, but S.79 excludes outdoor advertising structures (RSG, 2018), creating inconsistencies. The RSOSAA Law No.2 of 2015 imposes arbitrary fees, which conflict with valuation norms and the Nigerian Constitution (FGN, 1999). Therefore, a structured, fair taxation model is needed. The U.S. Internal Revenue Service (IRS) rules (Rev. Rul. 80-151, 1980; Whiteco; Sections 856[c][5][B]–[C], 856[d][1]) and international benchmarks (NYC Finance, 2022; Dubai Municipality, 2023; AMAC, 2015) guide cost-based, location-sensitive assessments and serve as a foundational structure in defining this standard’s valuation procedure.

Illustration

Using the cost approach equation, we can obtain the value in Table 7 as follows:

$$V_{bb} = f(L_v, B_v, P_v) \tag{1}$$

$$\therefore V_{bb} = \sum(\text{N}1,680,000 + \text{N}6,611,497.20 + \text{N}2,146,590.00) = \text{N} 10, 438, 087. 20$$

(Outdoor advertising structure asset value = land value + outdoor advertising structure value + permit value)

To determine the depreciation cost, the following straight-line formula is adopted:

$$\text{Straight-Line Depreciation Expense} = \text{Initial Cost} - \text{Salvage Value} / \text{Useful Life} \tag{2}$$

Given that the outdoor advertising structure is constructed with steel and concrete, the depreciation of these components will be uniform and joint. The components with these values: Display panel ~~N~~3,442,850.00, Stacked Steel display (Panel Faces) ~~N~~ 930,250.00, Catwalk platform ~~N~~305,000.00; Foundation reinforcement steel is ~~N~~166,890.00; Foundation concrete ~~N~~111,260 will depreciate simultaneously to present a single terminal date of obsolescence.

Note: Initial cost less salvage value @ 20% divided by useful life = depreciation per annum

The initial cost of steel is ~~N~~4, 658,940.00, and its salvage value is ~~N~~931,788.20. The initial cost for concrete is ~~N~~111, 260.00, and its salvage value is ~~N~~22,252.00.

Existing physical status of the components:

$$(i) \text{ Steel: } (\text{N}4,658,940 - \text{N}931,788.20) = \text{N}3, 727,151.80$$

$$(ii) \text{ Concrete: } (\text{N}111,260 - \text{N} 22,252) = \text{N}89, 008$$

$$\text{Annual depreciation is approximately} \qquad \qquad \qquad = \text{N}50, 882.13 \text{ per annum}$$

$$= \frac{\text{N}3,727,151.80 + \text{N}89,008}{75 \text{ years}} = \frac{\text{N}4,619,311.80}{75 \text{ years}} \qquad \qquad \qquad = \text{N} 50,882.13 \text{ per annum}$$

Furthermore, we assume that the outdoor advertising structure is 6 years old.

$$\text{Hence, the cumulative depreciation in 6 years} \qquad \qquad \qquad = \text{N} 305,292.78.$$

Table 7: Proposed Valuation Procedure for Assessing Outdoor Advertising Structures for Taxation (Rating) Purposes in Rivers State using the Cost Approach to Test Policy Validity: “Compute the Net Annual Value/Rateable Value”

Existing Advertising Structure	Outdoor 18.61 m² @ ₦	(₦)	(₦)
(Single-face panel)	₦ 185,000/m ²		
(i)Display panel		3,442,850	
(ii)Foundation	(Provisional sum)	278,150	
Add for No. of Additional faces	Nil	-	
		3,721,000	
Sub-total for the panel faces			
Add for		930,250	
(i) Stacked steel display at 25 % of ₦ 3,721,000 (panel faces)		305,000	
		[4,956,250]	
(ii)Catwalk platform 6.1 m @ N50,000/m		186,050	
			= 4,770,200
Subtotal for the Tangible Cost		[4,770,200]	
		2,146,590	
Less for no illumination @ 5% of ₦ 3,721,000 (Panel Face(s))		2,146,590	
			= 9,063,380
Subtotal for the Base Cost		4,293,180	
Add the intangible costs:			
Including Permit and Professional fees: Legal, accounting, engineering, and management fees. @ 45 % of ₦ 4,770,200 (Base Cost)			
Add the Investor's Entrepreneurial Profit @ 45 % of ₦4,770,200			
Subtotal for Intangible costs			
Current replacement cost of the structure (new)			
Less Estimated Accrued Depreciation:			

(a) Curable physical defects (Damage) in 6 years @ 20 %	-	Nil	
(b) Incurable physical defects in 6 years @ 20% :			
i) Fabricated steel with a 75- year remaining life span {(N4,658,940 – (N3,727,151.80/75 x 6) N931,788.20)/75 x 6}		298,172.14.	= 8,758,087.22
ii) Concrete and others {(N111,260 – N22,252)/75 x 6}	{N 89,008}/75 x 6}	7,120.64	
Subtotal of the depreciation		305,292.78	
Depreciated Replacement Cost of the Structure			
Add Lease Value for Land approx. 20.16 m ² let for N 5,000/m ² @ 6 %	N 100,800 × 16.6667		= 1,680,000.00
			= 10,438,087.22
Effective Capital Value (Depreciated Capital Value) of OAS			
Note: Gross value (inclusive of liabilities) refers to the gross rate-able value or gross yield on the capital invested. The gross yield @ 6% is considered appropriate for commercial properties in the state of Rivers.			
Gross Value @ 6 % of Effective Capital Value			= 626,284.00
Less Statutory Deductions (Outgoings) @ 16.44% of Gross Flow			= 102,943.00
Net operating income (net annual value = rate-able value) @ 5% yield on ECV			= 523,341.40.
∴ Rate-able value is rounded up to			= 523,341.00

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 7 presents a cost-based valuation for outdoor advertising structures in Rivers State, starting with a base cost of ₦3,721,000. After adjustments, deductions, and the addition of intangible costs and entrepreneurial profit, the depreciated replacement cost is ₦8,758,087.22. The final capital value is ₦10,438,087.22, yielding a net annual value of ₦523,341.00.

D. Determination of the Tax Rate or Rate Nairage

A tax rate determines the amount taxed, defined by government policy for property under ad valorem or area-based systems. It is set by the Local Government Legislative Assembly and published in the Gazette. The current

AMAC Bye-Law (2015) rates range from 3% to 7% for various properties. The system operates based on the following mathematical formula:

$$R = \frac{(T - C)}{V} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where: R = Tax Rate/Standardised Rate (Rate Nairage);

T = total budget (revenue from all sources);

C = Total income from other sources, except for outdoor advertising structure;

V = total rate-able values for all outdoor advertising structures; and

Illustration 1:

Assuming that the budget for the Port Harcourt Local Government for 2024 fiscal year 2024 is ₦100,000,000, and its revenue from other sources is ₦95,000,000. The total value for all Outdoor advertising structures is ₦40,000,000, the rate nairage equation becomes as follows:

$$R = \frac{(\text{₦}100,000,000 - \text{₦}95,000,000)}{\text{₦}40,000,000} \times 100$$

$$R = \frac{(\text{₦}5,000,000)}{\text{₦}40,000,000} \times 100$$

Tax rate = 12.5%

E. Assessment of the Payable Local Tax Amount

The "Local Tax" for outdoor advertising structures is determined by the tax rate (12.5%) and assessed rate-able Value (₦523,341), resulting in a tax amount of ₦65,418.00, as shown below:

Illustration 2:

From this equation based on the established economic rule:

Tax Amount = Rate-able Value x Tax Rate

Where: Net Operating Income or Net Annual Value or

Rateable value extracted from the valuation = ₦ 523,341.00

The tax rate determined from the budget deficit to

Assessed ratable values of the asset ratio = 12.5%

Tax Amount or Local Tax payable is ₦ 523,341.00 x 0.125 = ₦ 65,417.625

Tax Amount or Local Tax Rate payable rounded up to = ₦ 65,418.00

Illustration 3:

The equation below is also applied to determine the appropriateness of the tax rate used. Since this rate should be fixed without ambiguity, the mathematical formula that defines the function of each factor in the equation below and is used globally is considered appropriate for adoption as follows:

$$\text{Tax Rate} = \frac{\text{Tax Amount}}{\text{Price before Tax}} \times 100 \%$$

Where:

Price before tax, gross rent, or gross value

The tax rate is the ratio at which a is taxed;

The tax amount is the local tax rate or tax paid.

$$\text{Tax Rate} = \frac{\text{₦}65,418.00}{\text{₦}523,341.00} \times 100\%$$

$$\text{Tax Rate} = 0.1250007166 \times 100$$

Tax rate = 12.5%

The tax amount, tax rate, and market value can be deduced from the above equations where any variable is not known. The relationship between these variables is further expressed using details from the valuation to test its appropriateness.

However, under the current system using AMAC Bye-Law, 2015, considered more detailed than the Rivers State Local Law, No.5, 2018, a tax rate of 4% is prescribed for commercial properties. However, using the established rate-able Value of ₦523,341.00 determined in the valuation above, with the two tax rates operating separately, the appropriate approach is shown below:

- i. The tax amount is developed on a yield of 6% of the effective capital value of ₦10,438,087.22 to “establish the gross value of ₦626,284.00” for commercial properties as specified in AMAC Bye-Law, 2015, Ss. 14(1),15(1).
- ii. This is depreciated to allow for statutory deductions (outgoings) 16.44% gross value of ₦626,284.00” to “establish the net annual value @ 5% of effective capital value which becomes the rate-able value of ₦523,341.00” for commercial properties in the area.
- iii. Hence, the tax amount or standardized rate for the outdoor advertising structure whose value is ₦523,341.00 @ 12.5% = ₦65,418.00 (RSG, 2015).

A critical analysis of the details in items (i)–(iii) above shows that the rate-able value or net annual value, in this case hypothetical, represents the actual rental price of the property and is based on court pronouncements over the years (Opara, 2013). Hence, the above procedure is considered appropriate.

From the above analysis, multiplying the 12.5% with the assessed gross value gives the Tax Amount (Standardized Rate) payable for the single-face outdoor advertising structure as a commercial property valued for rating purposes. This procedure aligns with the established standard of practice for rating applied globally in similar situations and provides a guideline for amending the arbitrary tax rate of 4% specified in the AMAC Bye-Law (yet to be implemented in any region) and other related laws enacted if adopted.

Note: This rate is based on the above hypothetical values. However, it is important to state that this is the procedure established to fix the rates payable for real properties, including outdoor advertising structures, in Rivers State.

This comprehensive implementation plan details protocols, ensuring that the framework is practical, actionable, and ready for deployment.

Phase 3: Legislative approval and enforcement

This phase requires the monitoring of the bill for framework effectiveness and continuous improvements based on feedback and changing market conditions. To create detailed guidelines that Estate Surveyors and Valuers can follow when assessing the rates of outdoor advertising structure (FGN, 2004c). This should include instructions on data collection, valuation method application, and reporting.

- i. **Training and Capacity Building:** Develop training programs for Estate Surveyors and Valuers to ensure they are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively implement the new framework.
- ii. **Pilot Testing:** Pilot tests were conducted in select areas within Rivers State to validate the framework. Gather feedback from practitioners and stakeholders to refine the process.
- iii. **Documentation:** Prepare comprehensive documentation of the framework, including its rationale, design, and protocols.
- iv. **Policy Advocacy:** Engage with policymakers, local government authorities, and professional bodies to promote the adoption of the framework as a standard practice for OAS rating in Rivers State.
- v. **Legislative Alignment:** The framework should be aligned with existing and future legislation to ensure its long-term sustainability and legal standing.
- vi. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Establish mechanisms for the ongoing evaluation of the framework’s performance. This includes regular reviews of the valuation outcomes and stakeholders’ feedback.
- vii. **Feedback Mechanism:** Implement a system for receiving and addressing feedback from Estate Surveyors and Valuers, owners of outdoor advertising structures, and other stakeholders.

- viii. **Continuous Refinement:** Based on the evaluation results and feedback, make necessary adjustments to the framework to improve accuracy, fairness, and compliance with evolving legal standards. When implemented, this dynamic framework will remain effective and relevant, adapting to changes in legislation, market conditions, and stakeholder needs.

Figure 2: Validated Framework for Determining Local Tax Payable for Outdoor Advertising Structures in the Rivers State

Source: Adapted and modified from Akujuru (2014)

5. Interpretation and Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the current state of OAS taxation in Rivers State and the perceptions of various stakeholders regarding the existing tax framework. The survey data and qualitative insights highlight several areas where the current taxation system fails to meet its objectives and identify opportunities for improvement (Ogbonna & Appah, 2016; IMF, 2020).

The survey results reveal that a significant proportion of respondents (37.3%) disagreed with the clarity and definition of the tax laws in Rivers State, and 33.3% were undecided. This ambiguity in the tax laws, with a mean score of 1.92 and a standard deviation of 0.815, suggests that stakeholders are unsure about the effectiveness and comprehensibility of the existing legislation (Chowdhury, 2014; RSG, 2015). Moreover, a large majority (70%) strongly disagreed that the legislation is regularly updated to reflect economic and social changes, as evidenced by a mean of 1.30 and a standard deviation of 0.460. These results underscore the need for clearer and more up-to-date tax laws that can adapt to changing market conditions (Musgrave, 1959; OECD, 2010).

The findings on taxation fairness and enforcement reveal significant dissatisfaction with the current system. All respondents (100%) strongly disagreed with statements regarding the fairness of the taxation system and the effectiveness of local government enforcement. These findings suggest systemic inequities and weak implementation of tax laws, indicating that local government authorities are either unwilling or unable to effectively manage the taxation process (Kagan, Uradu & Munichiello, 2021; Ogundipe, 2022). The lack of trust in enforcement mechanisms further emphasizes the need for better coordination between local and state authorities, as well as for improved enforcement capabilities (OECD, 2010; IMF, 2020). While there was a relatively high level of public awareness about tax regulations on the structure of outdoor advertising (81.3% strongly agreed), the study also uncovered contradictions between awareness and actual understanding (Atkinson & Stiglitz, 1976). This shows that stakeholders may be aware of the regulations but do not fully comprehend them, which could contribute to non-compliance or confusion (Kaplow, 2008). Although a high percentage of respondents (85.3%) agreed that penalties for non-compliance are sufficient, the lack of effective enforcement continues to undermine their impact (Deloitte, 2011; George & Akujuru, 2022).

The current tax framework places a significant financial burden on advertizers, with 54% of respondents agreeing that the tax system imposes substantial costs (Obialo, 2025). However, the unanimous disagreement regarding whether taxes generate meaningful revenue for local governments reveals a major flaw in the system (Owusu, 2015). The lack of reinvestment of tax revenue into local infrastructure, as suggested by strong disagreement (Mean = 1.00) with this statement, reflects inefficiencies in the allocation and use of tax funds (Ogbonna & Appah, 2016). This inefficiency further limits the tax system's potential benefits for local businesses and urban development (Otto & Ukpere, 2014).

Qualitative insights from the interviews revealed significant legal inconsistencies, particularly contradictions between local laws (RSOSAL No. 2/2015) and national laws, leading to confusion and arbitrary enforcement (RSG, 2015; FGN, 1999). Furthermore, stakeholders identified a 300% variation in tax rates across different LGAs, which deepens concerns about inequity in the tax system (Boluwatife, 2024). The lack of uniformity in tax application and the absence of clear guidelines have led to widespread confusion and uncertainty among stakeholders (Akujuru, 2014; Bailey, 2018).

Another significant issue identified in the interviews is the jurisdictional conflict between state and local authorities, particularly regarding the exclusion of OAS from the tenement rate framework (AMAC, 2012; George & Akujuru, 2022). This creates a paradox where OAS are recognized as taxable assets but excluded from

valuation frameworks, resulting in arbitrary fees and inconsistent tax collection practices (Nation & Oehlrich, 1999; Nnah & Owei, 2007).

The study emphasizes the need to resolve these jurisdictional conflicts and harmonize the mandates of state and local governments (RSG, 2018; FGN, 1998). Additionally, it assessed stakeholder perceptions regarding potential reforms to the OA taxation system. The majority of respondents expressed strong support for adopting a standardized tax framework, which would reduce ambiguity and enhance fairness in the taxation process (Kenton & Uradu, 2020; Oni *et al.*, 2019).

The implementation of international best practices, such as GIS-based digital registries and zoning-based adjustments, was supported. These solutions aim to standardize valuations, ensure fair assessments, and improve transparency in the tax process (IASB, 2013; OECD, 2010). A significant number of respondents also indicated their support for integrating advanced technology, such as digital filing and data analytics, to enhance tax administration efficiency and transparency (NITDA, 2007; IMF, 2020).

Furthermore, stakeholders emphasized the need for regular public consultations, stakeholder engagement, and periodic audits to ensure that the tax system remains effective and equitable (Payne & Raiborn, 2018; Kaushik & Walsh, 2019). While there was general agreement on the importance of a standardized tax framework, some skepticism was noted about the feasibility of implementing such reforms, as indicated by the 51.3% undecided response regarding local government collaboration. This shows that, despite broad support for reforms, there are concerns about the political will and capacity of local authorities to effectively implement these changes (RSG, 2024b; Kumar, 2024).

Conclusion

This study has provided valuable insights into the current state of the taxation of outdoor advertising structure in Rivers State, highlighting several critical challenges and proposing actionable solutions for reform. The findings emphasize the need for a comprehensive review of the existing legislative framework, as there is widespread dissatisfaction with the current tax laws' clarity, fairness, and enforcement. Significant legal inconsistencies, arbitrary taxation, and jurisdictional conflicts between state and local authorities have created an environment of confusion and inequity, hindering the taxation system's effectiveness. Despite these challenges, the study reveals that stakeholders are open to reform, showing strong support for a standardized tax framework, the adoption of international best practices, and the integration of advanced technology to streamline tax administration. There is a widespread consensus on the importance of stakeholder engagement and the necessity for regular audits and capacity building, which further strengthens the need for a more transparent and equitable system. The proposed policy framework includes harmonizing state and local government laws, adopting digital tools for improved tax administration, and establishing clear guidelines for tax assessments. This framework provides a roadmap for transforming the state's taxation system. Rivers State can create a more efficient, fair, and sustainable tax regime that benefits both the advertising industry and the local community by addressing these systemic issues and prioritizing collaboration among stakeholders. In conclusion, the study emphasizes the urgent need for legislative and administrative reforms to ensure that the state's outdoor advertising taxation system is both effective and equitable. If implemented, the proposed reforms could enhance revenue generation, promote industry growth, and improve urban esthetics, ultimately contributing to the state's economic development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

- i. Implementation of this Standardized Framework: Implementing this structured framework for local tax payable on outdoor advertising structure using the cost approach in the valuation on the basis of fair value assessment guidelines will ensure that rates are consistent and transparent across the board.
- ii. Legislative Reform: Resolve conflicts between the Federal - NURP Act, Cap N138, LFN, 2004, S.91 (FGN, 2004); Land Use Act, Cap L.5, LFN, 2004, Ss. 29(4), 51 (FGN, 2004); The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, (per S.7(5), 4th Schedule, Items 1(j),(k)(i),(ii)) 1999, (as amended) and State laws by amending the Rivers Law No. 2 (2015) to clarify the roles of LGA and S.79 (RSG, 2018, 34), qualifying outdoor advertising structures as real property.
- iii. Operational Improvement: Phase 1: Deploy GIS-based digital inventories (92% recommendation) to address data gaps. Phase 2 - Pilot-test in 2 LGAs to refine enforcement. Implement digital payment systems and analytics tools. Moreover, ensure regular training for local government officials to enhance their capacity in effectively administering the tax framework.
- iv. Stakeholder Engagement: Involve relevant stakeholders, including local government officials, Estate Surveyors and Valuers, and owners of outdoor advertising structures, including their landlords, in the development and review of the taxation framework to ensure that it reflects their insights and concerns. This is by launching awareness campaigns to explain technical concepts, which will further build the required market evidence.
- v. Periodic Audits and Reviews: Conduct regular audits and evaluations of the tax framework to maintain its effectiveness and fairness, ensuring that it adapts to changing economic conditions and stakeholders' needs.
- vi. Proper Documentation: Ensure that tax policies are clearly documented and communicated to all stakeholders to promote transparency and compliance.
- vii. The study recommends enacting a standardized, cost-based market value tax framework, supported by legislative reform to resolve jurisdictional overlaps. Operational improvements such as GIS systems, digital payments, and pilot-testing in selected LGAs are vital. Stakeholder engagement, periodic audits, and capacity building will enhance compliance and policy effectiveness, ensuring sustainable urban tax governance.

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